

ENGLISH AND UZBEK TOPONYMIC PHRASEOLOGICAL UNIT: LINGUOCULTURAL

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of English and Uzbek phraseological units, including place names. Attempts are being made to identify the sources of origin, as well as to analyze them from a linguocultural perspective. Toponymic phraseological units in both languages are divided into five main groups according to their sources of origin, and special attention is paid to historically connected phraseological units. Phraseological units based on specific historical events and facts are opened and explained here. The author suggests two major groups for the presence of real place names in phraseological units. The toponymic properties of real toponyms in the sense of the corresponding noun and phraseological unit have also been identified. There are also additional connotations of toponyms that affect the meaning of phraseological units. Examples are taken from a number of phraseological and paremiological dictionaries in English and Uzbek. Examples are analyzed by descriptive and comparative methods. Similarities and differences are identified based on the national and cultural characteristics of the two languages.

Toponymy is an integral part of onomastics, which studies geographical names (toponyms), their meaning, structure, origin and distribution. The set of toponyms in any territory constitutes its toponymy (Nikonov, 2011). Traditionally, a toponym means the proper name of any geographical object, any object on the surface of the Earth or in its depths, identified by a person as an independent unit (Superanskaya, 1984), Davletkulova (2014) defines toponyms as “historically, socially and culturally defined geographical names of any natural or artificial objects created by man on land or on the water territory of the Earth. Geographical names are very stable, they persist for a long time, becoming a kind of historical monuments; therefore, toponymy, according to many researchers, also to a certain extent refers to history and source study (Nikonov, 2011; Garaeva, 2014). The status of a toponym is determined by its main functions in the linguistic culture of an ethnos: a) nominative (naming); b) individualizing (identification); c) cumulative; d) cultural content (Sedykh et al.,

2020). Nikonov (2011) in his work "Introduction to Toponyms" identifies three semantic planes of toponyms: pre-toponymic, toponymic proper, and post-toponymic. (it has nothing to do with the first, since it lies in a different plane) 3) the ottoponymic (posttoponymic) meaning is the associations that connect people with a name as a result of acquaintance with an object. It is vitally important to know the post-toponymic meaning, since the meanings of pus with a toponymic element are based on it. Maslova (2005) emphasizes the role of background knowledge in the use of phraseological units with the constituent parts of a proper name, stating that the denotative aspect plays an important role in the meaning of phraseological units containing proper names. These phraseological units reflect the history of people; therefore, to understand them, you need to know specific historical facts. In all languages of the world, many phraseological units are based on the names of cities, streets, rivers, oceans, as well as on the realities associated with toponyms. PU with a toponymic component reflect a person's centuries-old observations of the world of toponymy, convey the attitude of people to this sphere of reality (Gilyazeva, Bazarova, 2018; Nefedova, 2014).

There are many place names formed as part of the PU. It is important to examine how and when they appeared, as well as the determinants of their appearance. In some cases, these PUs undergo semantic transformations over time. Consequently, in the study of such phraseological units, the motivation and etymology of toponymic components play a vital role. In the process of researching the sources of origin, the following groups of software were discovered: Shipshape and Bristol fashion - for everything to be in order (in the middle of the 19th century, Bristol was known as a port city in England. The expression emphasized the commercial prosperity of the port of Bristol and its good navigation conditions) (Shitova, 2012; Rezanova, Khlebnikova, 2015) cross the Rubicon - take irreversible action (The Rubicon was a small river in northeastern Italy. By moving his army across the Rubicon to Italy in 49 BC, Julius Caesar violated the law forbidding a general to withdraw an army from his own province, and therefore entered the war against the Senate and Pompey (Judith, 2004) In Uzbek: gap quvgan baloga yo'liqar, yo'l quvgan G'aznaga - the expression refers to the fact that Ghazna was one of the cultural, political and commercial centers of Central Asia in the Middle In most cases, the meaning of such units is closely related to the origin of PU. Thus, PU with onomastic components are an important source of information about history, culture and tradition X. ofa Russian ethnos (Khudoyorova, 2020; Shoikova, Tikhonova, 2014).

PEs have combined customs, traditions and everyday life. Be Complete / Talk Blarney - make incomprehensible promises, flatter and deceive. The Blarney stone is a stone of the same name in Ireland. By tradition, kissing this stone, a person acquires the ability to charm and convince people (Shitova, 2012). In the Uzbek language there is PE with toponymic components related to customs and everyday life: Beva xotinga Buxorodan it huradi- so that the widow should live alone, as they gossip about her; Eshonbozorda it olsa "yigirma" sidan kuruk kolmaidi - a person who goes everywhere, especially for ceremonies (Eshonbozor is a village in the south of Kazakhstan, yigirma is a religious ceremony that is held after death); ahmoqqa Quva bir tosh - used when a person who does not do something completely and must do it again; PUs that came from other languages: idioms and borrowings It is almost impossible to find exact synonyms for such units in other languages, thus the toponymic Pus

are borrowed in most cases: in English, discover America also exists in Uzbek, Amerika ochmoq - to say or declare what has already been discovered; There are phraseological onions that exist in both languages, but in some cases they differ in meaning, for example, the Chinese wall means a barrier in English, since there has never been a unique plan for its construction, and in the Uzbek Xitoy devorimeans there is something stable and durable ... The two languages took into account different features of the same phenomenon. It should be emphasized that they are associated with world famous historical events and phenomena.

Archaic place names in PU In English and Uzbek languages, toponymic PU, which have archaic place names in their structure, eventually become archaic phraseological units: perfidious Albion is the nickname of England (Albion was the ancient name of Great Britain) (Kunin, 1984). Gap desang qop-qop, ish desang Ashtarxondan top - a boastful and extremely lazy person (Ashtarkhon was one of the khanates in the 15th century in Central Asia). Archaisms complicate the processes of use and understanding, even for native speakers. As you can see, simple knowledge of the name and geographical location of a place is not enough to understand the meaning of these units as specific historical events, socioeconomic and political situations associated with the toponym in the PU structure is reflected in their semantics. All such units are used metaphorically in both languages.

Distance between place names: The geographical position of places, especially distant ones, is reflected in the PU: from China to Peru - everywhere; from here to Timbuktu - distant lands; in Uzbek, dunyoning narigi chekkasi / dunyoning u burchagi means the same thing, but they do not contain place names. PU with fictitious place names Utopian dreams are beautiful but impractical plans. Utopia is a blessed country with an ideal socio-political and legal system. Thomas More describes a fantastic island in the Atlantic Ocean in his book Utopia (1516); Champs Elysees - paradise. Homer describes the Champs Elysees as a happy land in which blessed spirits live in the afterlife; the land of Cocaine is a dreamland of abundance and idleness, a paradise on earth (Kunin, 1984); Qasd qilgan - Qof tog'idan o'tar, Hasad qilgan - o'z oyog'idan yitar - if you admire, you will reach your goal, while envy leads to failure (Kof is a legendary mountain that is difficult to reach); amri padar - Arshdan alo - children are strongly encouraged to obey the orders of their father (according to religious beliefs, Arsh is a place in heaven, next to God). The vast majority of such units describe ideal and ideal places in which people enjoy living.

Conclusion: PUs containing place names in their structure have social, geographic and historical associations that are part of the background and communicative knowledge of native speakers. Facts and events of the distant past, religion, literature, customs and traditions of the nation stimulated the formation of ITS with an element of toponym. They contain culturally significant and historically related information, as a wide range of extralinguistic factors contributed to their origin. Thus, the national-cultural component of the toponym plays an important role in the semantics of such units. 2) Although most of the analyzed PU groups have similar characteristics, functions and come from the same sources in both languages, it is almost impossible to find exact parallels, except for international PU (biblical, mythological) in other languages, as they relate to unique - cultural concepts and realities every nation. Place names have various meanings and connotations due to culture

specific associations. Symbolic and stereotypical meanings of place names that were formed for long periods of time affect the overall connotation of a unit. Thus, in toponymical phraseologies, whether the unit is positively or negatively marked heavily depends on the place name in the structure of a phraseological unit.

References:

1. Linguocultures.Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences,154, 130-137.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.10.124>
2. Nikonov, V.A., (2011) Introduction to Toponymy. Pub.2nded. –M.: Publishing LKI.
3. Rezanova, Z. I., & Khlebnikova, A. L. (2015). Gender metaphors in Russian and English linguocultures: a comparative study.
4. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences,215, 273278
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.634>
5. Sedykh, A., Marabini, A., Stryzhnova, M., Bolgova, E., & Bolgova, N. (2020). Toponymic phraseological unit, linguistic thinking and discourse: Russia, France and Italy.Revista Inclusiones, 488-500.
6. Shitova, L.F. (20120) Carry Coals to Newcastle. 350 Geographic idioms and more. SPb. Anthropology.
7. Shoikova, A. M., & Tikhonova, E. V. (2014). The development of students' mental lexicon in legal discourse by means of authentic materials.Procedia-Social And Behavioral Sciences,154, 522-526.
8. Shomaqsudov, Sh., & Shorahmedov, Sh., (1987) Why do we say so. Dictionary of Uzbek national proverbs. Tashkent.
9. Superanskaya, A.V., (1973) Genaral theory of proper nouns. Moscow:Nauka.1973.
10. Superanskaya, A.V., What is toponymy? Moscow: Nauka. 1984
11. Teliya, V.N., (1996) Russian phraseology. Semantic, pragmatic and lingual-cultural aspects. Moscow: Nauka.
12. To'lqinovna,X. S. (2020). Archaic And Historical Elements In English And Uzbek Phraseological Units.